

Research Trends, Challenges and Emerging Topics Of Cryptocurrency Forensics

1st Bhuvan Kumar
School of Computing Science
Engineering (SCSE)
VIT Bhopal University
Bhopal, India

2nd Dr Sarvanan D
School Of Computing Science
Engineering (SCSE)
VIT Bhopal University
Bhopal, India

3rd Dr Muneeswaran V
School of Computing Science
Engineering (SCSE)
VIT Bhopal University
Bhopal, India

4th Dr Rizwan Ur Rahman
School Of Computing Science
Engineering (SCSE)
VIT Bhopal University
Bhopal, India

Abstract—Cryptocurrency forensics has gotten a lot of interest from researchers and practitioners because of its importance in cybersecurity. The difficulty of evidence collecting, which frequently necessitates the use of multiple technologies, is closely tied to the increasing sophistication of modern cyberattacks. Researchers have provided numerous surveys and evaluations on the subject to date. However, such papers concentrated on the advancements of each unique domain of cryptocurrency forensics. As a result, while each of these surveys helps scholars and practitioners stay up to date on the newest achievements in a specific subject of digital forensics, a worldwide perspective is lacking. To close this gap, we conducted a qualitative evaluation of studies in the field of digital forensics and identified the main topics on cryptocurrency forensics and highlighted their primary challenges. Our analysis provides sufficient evidence to demonstrate that the digital forensics community might benefit from deeper cooperation and cross-topic research, as it is clear that scholars and practitioners are working on the same challenges at the same time, sometimes without realizing it.

Index terms- Cryptocurrency forensics, Cybersecurity, Forensic investigations

I. INTRODUCTION

The technique of examining and analysing bitcoin transactions in order to uncover and trace illegal activities is known as cryptocurrency forensics. It is a young industry, but it is expanding fast as the usage of bitcoin for criminal reasons grows.

Cryptocurrency transactions are recorded on a blockchain, which is a public ledger. This allows for the tracking of funds even when the identity of the persons involved are concealed. To evaluate blockchain data, cryptocurrency forensics investigators employ a range of methodologies. In the battle against cybercrime, cryptocurrency forensics is a crucial tool for law enforcement and financial institutions. It may be used to look into a wide range of crimes, including as money laundering, fraud, ransomware attacks, dark web marketplaces, and terrorism financing. As the usage of cryptocurrencies for illicit reasons grows, so will the demand for cryptocurrency forensics expertise. This is a fast-expanding field with a lot of room for expansion. Some of the challenges for cryptocurrency forensics are as follows-

- The anonymity of cryptocurrency transactions makes it difficult to identify the perpetrators of crimes.
- The complexity of blockchain technology can make it difficult to analyse cryptocurrency data.
- The lack of standardized procedures and tools can make it difficult to share information between different investigators.

Contribution and motivation: Digital evidence has become the standard and is used in the majority of modern criminal investigations. There is, however, digital evidence to which many procedures and methodologies apply. While certain concepts may stay constant, they cannot be applied to all sorts of evidence. For example, gathering evidence from the cloud has little relation to IoT or picture forensics. This has resulted in a massive quantity of research addressing the issues highlighted in each sector separately, with the majority of the work devoted to the creation of innovative tools and algorithms to extract digital evidence and intelligence from diverse sources. Currently, researchers are working hard to give a comprehensive review of the literature and developments in each topic through specialized surveys and reviews. Although these surveys are important the evidences are still missing. All the surveys are focused on a specific domain, challenges, issues and methods are not identified.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the research methodology of cryptocurrency forensics, Understanding and evaluating the complicated digital trails left by transactions in the world of bitcoin forensics necessitates a well-defined and extensive study technique. This section describes the methodology and approaches used to study and expose the hidden features of bitcoin transactions, addressing both technical and procedural parts of the research process.

Table 1- A summary of the research questions and the sections devoted to answering them.

Research Question	Objective
What is the current state of practice and research trends?	The goal is to uncover which issues researchers and practitioners are focusing their efforts on, so that we can identify both research trends and areas that require further assistance. It will also streamline common solutions and practices that may be promoted by other areas.
Which are the current challenges in Cryptocurrency forensics?	Cryptocurrency forensics faces challenges due to pseudonymity, privacy issues, decentralized nature, large transaction volumes, mixer services, developing technology, exchange complications, encryption, resource intensity, lack of standardization, regulatory uncertainty, and an educational gap, cryptocurrency forensics confronts hurdles.
Is the current state of the art aligned with technological evolution in cryptocurrency forensics?	The goal is to determine if the current state of the art, in terms of technology, regulations, and standards, is adequate to deal with modern cybercrime. This may be used as a guideline for tool creation.
What strategies should be used to deal with identified challenges?	Our strategy is to identify the pain points of the current state of practice and use a gap analysis to propose effective tactics based on the information acquired from the state of the art.

A. Search strategy

As previously stated, our entire survey approach is based on a set of predetermined research questions related to the cryptocurrency forensics literature. Based on these study topics, we did substantial research addressing the different technical/functional/security difficulties of the cryptocurrency forensics literature.

Figure 1- Detail of the research methodology steps.

III. TAXONOMY OF CHALLENGES-BASED ON CRYPTOCURRENCY FORENSICS RESEARCH

The themes of this categorization were methodically chosen based on the contents of the examined literature, and so reflect the cryptocurrency forensics research landscape and demonstrate the variability of cryptocurrency forensic solutions with great fidelity. Figure 2 depicts a graphical representation of the classification of cryptocurrency forensics issues. We explore the key limits and difficulties offered in the literature in each scenario.

A. Blockchain

Blockchain technology has been regularly incorporated into existing systems or utilized as the foundation for rebuilding systems from the ground up in a variety of fields. Aside from the financial arena to which it was first used, blockchain technology is being employed in a variety of other use cases such as supply chain management, cybersecurity enhancement, document/certificate validation, crowdfunding campaigns, and more. Furthermore, because blockchain-based financial systems allow greater secrecy than traditional payment methods, cryptocurrencies are frequently employed in illicit operations. This necessitates the use of blockchain forensics approaches due to the vast volume of data kept in blockchain systems and the number of processes controlled by such systems. The primary feature of blockchain-based systems is the assurance of data integrity, which is directly tied to forensic analysis. On the one hand, this characteristic makes forensic analysis easier to manage. However, this may complicate the process because consumers may be more cautious while working with such technologies.

Figure 2- Challenges-based and domain-specific of Cryptocurrency forensics topics identified in the literature

Table 2- Challenges and Limitation and a brief description of Blockchain.

Challenge/Limitation	Description
Scalability	Blockchain networks can struggle to manage a high volume of

	transactions per second, resulting in longer confirmation times.
Security Vulnerabilities	Blockchain protocols and smart contracts
Privacy and Anonymity	While transactions are pseudonymous blockchain records are public, allowing users to be tracked and analyzed
Immutability	Once data is stored on a blockchain, it is almost hard to change, which might be problematic in the event of an error or a disagreement.

B. Hardware Wallets

Hardware wallets are specialized devices that are meant to securely store and manage bitcoin private keys in the cloud. They offer a high level of security and are largely regarded as one of the safest ways to store and secure bitcoins. The following is how hardware wallets function in the context of cryptocurrency. Cryptocurrencies use a public-private key pair method to operate.

The private key is a code that allows you to access your bitcoin assets. This private key is stored offline by hardware wallets, making it unavailable to potential internet risks such as hacking or malware.

- **Offline Operation-** During normal use, hardware wallets are not linked to the internet. This separation from online networks significantly minimizes the possibility of remote assaults on your private keys. It also implies that even if your PC is hacked, your bitcoin is safe on the hardware wallet.
- Avoid combining SI and CGS units, such as current in amperes and magnetic field in oersted. This often leads to confusion because equations do not balance dimensionally. If you must use mixed units, clearly state the units for each quantity that you use in an equation.
- **Security Mechanisms-** Hardware wallets have a variety of security mechanisms to safeguard your private keys. Secure element chips, PIN codes, and passcode protection are frequently used. Some devices additionally have a physical confirmation button that must be hit in order to authorize transactions, providing an additional degree of security.

Table 3- Challenges and Limitation and a brief description of Hardware wallets.

<i>Challenge/Limitation</i>	<i>Description</i>
Cost	Hardware wallets have a one-time purchase cost, which might be too expensive for certain users, particularly those with low finances or tiny bitcoin holdings.

Initial Setup	For newcomers, setting up a hardware wallet may be quite complicated, requiring the development of a recovery seed and guaranteeing its secure storage. Users must also remember their PINs and passwords.
Compatibility	Some coins and tokens may not be supported by hardware wallets. Users should ensure that their device is compatible with their individual bitcoin holdings.
Limited Support	Customer assistance is provided by hardware wallet makers; however, it may not be as readily available or fast as support for popular financial services or software apps.

C. Private Coins

Digital currencies called "privacy coins," often referred to as "anonymous cryptocurrencies" or "privacy-focused cryptocurrencies," are created to increase the secrecy and anonymity of transactions on certain blockchain networks. Monero (XMR), Zcash (ZEC), and Dash (DASH) are some well-known examples of privacy cryptocurrencies. These currencies use a variety of cryptographic methods to obscure transaction data, making it difficult to track and analyze transactions. Privacy coins, on the other hand, bring new issues and concerns in the realm of cryptocurrency forensics:

- **Transaction Likability-** While privacy coins guarantee high transaction privacy, if not used appropriately, certain parts of transactions can still be connected. Forensic specialists may search for patterns or errors that might provide information about the people involved.
- **Exchange Challenges-** Due to their enhanced privacy features, privacy coins can be difficult for cryptocurrency exchanges to handle. Because of regulatory concerns, several exchanges prefer to delist or limit trade of privacy coins, making it more difficult to monitor transactions on these networks.
- **Forensic Tools and Techniques-** To accommodate privacy coins, the discipline of cryptocurrency forensics is expanding. Although the amount of success varies based on the coin and transaction, forensic specialists are creating new tools and strategies to examine privacy coin transactions.

Table 4- Challenges and Limitation and a brief description of Privacy coin.

<i>Challenge/Limitation</i>	<i>Description</i>
Transaction Privacy	Privacy coins are designed to guarantee robust transaction privacy, making it difficult for forensic researchers to track the source, destination, and value of transactions.

Evolving Forensic Techniques	Cryptocurrency forensics is changing to include privacy currencies. With different degrees of effectiveness, forensic specialists are inventing new tools and procedures to analyse and trace transactions.
Blockchain Analytics	Regardless of privacy characteristics, blockchain analytics firms are working on detecting trends and weaknesses in privacy coin transactions, with varied degrees of success.
Legal and Regulatory Uncertainty	In various jurisdictions, privacy coins raise legal and regulatory concerns. Some governments have prohibited or limited their usage, complicating forensic investigations.

D. Limited Legal Framework

In many places, the legal framework around cryptocurrency forensics is still emerging and might be quite restricted. Here are some major considerations concerning the legal framework's constraints on cryptocurrency forensics:

- **Lack of Clarity:** - One of the most significant issues is the lack of clear and thorough legislation dedicated exclusively to cryptocurrency forensics. Cryptocurrencies are a relatively new technology, and authorities have struggled to keep up with the space's rapid evolution.
- **Changing Landscape:** - The bitcoin market is always changing as new technology and privacy-enhancing features are introduced. It is difficult for legal frameworks to keep up with growing risks and vulnerabilities in this dynamic environment.
- **Privacy Concerns:** - Accessing transaction data and wallet information is made difficult by privacy-focused coins and technology. While privacy is important, it can make it difficult for law enforcement and forensic professionals to undertake investigations.

Table 5- Challenges and Limitation and a brief description of Limited legal framework

<i>Challenge/Limitation</i>	<i>Description</i>
Lack of Clarity	There are no clear and comprehensive regulations governing cryptocurrency forensics. Regulators sometimes struggle to keep up with the fast-paced changes in the crypto field.
Legal Challenges in Recovery	The process of recovering stolen or illegally obtained cryptocurrencies can be legally complex, and asset recovery methods may be ineffective or not well-established.
Resource Constraints	Many law enforcement organizations and regulatory bodies lack the resources and

	experience required for bitcoin forensics, which may be time-consuming.
Jurisdictional Variation	The legal framework differs greatly by nation, with some countries welcoming cryptocurrencies while others enforcing tight restrictions or remaining dubious about regulation.

E. Global nature of cryptocurrency crime

Cryptocurrency crime is a worldwide phenomenon with distinct characteristics that make typical law enforcement and regulatory efforts difficult to tackle. In the context of cryptocurrency forensics, below are some essential features of the worldwide nature of cryptocurrency crime:

- **Money Laundering** - Cryptocurrencies have the potential to be used to launder money across borders. Criminals may transit illicit cash across several cryptocurrencies, combining services and exchanges in different jurisdictions, making tracing and monitoring difficult.
- **Cybersecurity Threats** - Cryptocurrencies are frequently used by cybercriminals to demand ransom payments in return for releasing data or unlocking infected computers. These ransomware assaults have the potential to target businesses and individuals all around the world, adding to the global aspect of cryptocurrency crime.
- **Darknet Markets** - On darknet markets, cryptocurrency is regularly used to acquire illicit products and services. These marketplaces are available worldwide, allowing individuals to participate in unlawful acts while remaining anonymous.

Table 6- Challenges and Limitation and a brief description of Global nature of cryptocurrency crime.

<i>Challenge/Limitation</i>	<i>Description</i>
Legal Jurisdiction	Determining the proper legal jurisdiction for investigating and prosecuting cryptocurrency crimes may be difficult and may lead to legal issues.
Cross-Border Money Laundering	Criminals use cryptocurrencies' borderless character for money laundering, complicating efforts to detect and monitor the origin of illegal payments across various jurisdictions.
Privacy-Enhancing Technologies	Privacy-focused cryptocurrencies and technology can make it difficult for investigators to track down transactions and identify persons involved in criminal activity.
International Collaboration	While international cooperation is necessary, coordinating activities and sharing information among law enforcement organizations working in various nations may be difficult.

F. Cybersecurity Threat

Cryptocurrency crime is a worldwide phenomenon with distinct characteristics that make typical law enforcement and regulatory efforts difficult to tackle. In the context of bitcoin forensics, below are some essential features of the worldwide nature of cryptocurrency crime:

- **Borderless Transactions:** Because cryptocurrency is digital, it is essentially borderless. They can be easily transferred and received by persons and companies in multiple countries, making it impossible for any single state to properly manage or regulate them.
- **Decentralization:** Because many cryptocurrencies function on decentralized blockchain networks, it is difficult to identify a central authority or institution accountable for network maintenance. The activities of regulators and law enforcement authorities may be hampered as a result of this decentralization.
- **Crypto jacking:** The illegal use of a victim's computational resources to mine cryptocurrency is known as crypto jacking. While this danger primarily affects the victim's resources, it may also be utilized by criminals to create bitcoin anonymously.

Table 7- Challenges and Limitation and a brief description of Cybersecurity threats.

Challenge/Limitation	Description
Phishing Attacks	Phishing attempts deceive people into disclosing private keys and personal information, jeopardizing the security of their bitcoin holdings.
Ransomware	Ransomware attacks encrypt data and demand bitcoin ransoms, making it difficult to track down and recover cash while disrupting operations.
Darknet Markets	On darknet marketplaces, cryptocurrency is utilized for unlawful operations, taking advantage of cryptocurrency's anonymity.
Exchange Vulnerabilities	Vulnerabilities in bitcoin exchanges can result in breaches and illegal access, leading to losses and forensic complications.

IV. CRYPTOCURRENCY FORENSICS METHODOLOGIES, PRACTICES AND STANDARDS

Cryptocurrency forensics, also known as blockchain forensics, is the examination and analysis of cryptocurrency transaction, addresses and activities such as Bitcoin, Ethereum and others. The demand for effective forensic procedures, processes, and standards developed in tandem with the rise in cryptocurrency use. It critical in the investigation and prosecution of cryptocurrency-related crimes like as money laundering, fraud and ransomware attacks

A. Cryptocurrency Forensics Methodologies

Cryptocurrency forensics is an advanced field that involves the examination and analysis of cryptocurrency transactions, addresses, and activities such as Bitcoin, Ethereum, and others. The purpose is to discover and comprehend the movement of cash, identify persons involved, and track down illegal activity on blockchain networks. Cryptocurrency forensics is especially important in situations of fraud, money laundering, ransomware attacks, and other cryptocurrencies-related criminality.

- **Transaction Analysis:** Cryptocurrency forensics experts evaluate blockchain transactions to follow the movement of funds, identify addresses involved, and link various cryptocurrency wallets. To link bitcoin activities to real-world persons or businesses, techniques like as address tagging, wallet attribution, and transaction analysis are used.
- **Use of Specialized Tools:** Investigating dark web markets and other illicit bitcoin activity sometimes necessitates the use of specialized tools and platforms built for cryptocurrency analysis. These technologies assist investigators in following up on suspected transactions, identifying patterns, and gathering evidence of unlawful activity.
- **Compliance with judicial and Privacy criteria:** To secure the admission of evidence in judicial proceedings, cryptocurrency forensic investigations must comply with legal and privacy criteria.
- **Detecting Crypto-Related Crimes:** Forensic investigators can monitor and understand the movement of bitcoin assets on the blockchain. To unlock wallets or addresses of interest, digital forensics may be used to trace browser history searches, addresses, or crypto transactions, as well as evaluate system or user artifacts.

B. Cryptocurrency forensics Frameworks

To give an organized approach to the digital currency forensics, a number of frameworks and recommendations have been created. These frameworks assist investigators, law enforcement, and other stakeholders in conducting and analyzing investigations in a systematic manner. The following are some major cryptocurrency forensic frameworks:

CHAINALYSIS Reactor

- Reactor is a cryptocurrency analysis program developed by Chainalysis that provides a platform for studying blockchain data.
- It aids in the tracking of transactions, the identification of trends, and the assignment of bitcoin addresses to real-world organizations.
- The framework aids in compliance and investigations involving fraud, money laundering, and other illegal actions.

CRYPTOOLS:

- CRYPTOOLS is a Dutch police open-source platform that offers tools for cryptocurrency investigations.

- It provides tools for address grouping, transaction analysis, and visualizing blockchain data.
- The framework is intended to aid law enforcement authorities in their investigations into cryptocurrencies.

Financial Action Task Force (FATF) Guidelines:

- The Financial Action Task Force (FATF) is an intergovernmental body that establishes worldwide guidelines for combatting money laundering and terrorism funding.
- The FATF offers guidelines on virtual assets and virtual asset service providers (VASPs), highlighting the need of nations regulating and supervising cryptocurrency-related activity.

Interpol Digital Forensics Framework:

- Interpol provides a generic framework for digital forensics that may be tailored to bitcoin investigations.
- It focuses on the significance of good evidence handling, forensic analysis, and international cooperation.

National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) Cybersecurity Framework:

- The NIST Cybersecurity Framework, while not particular to cryptocurrency forensics, provides a holistic method to maintaining and strengthening an organization's cybersecurity posture.
- The framework's components may be customized to investigate cybersecurity events using cryptocurrency.

ISO/IEC Standards:

- Digital forensics standards from the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) and the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) can be used to cryptocurrency investigations.
- ISO/IEC 27037, for example, specifies procedures for identifying, gathering, acquiring, and archiving digital evidence.

C. Cryptocurrency Forensics Process Model

Cryptocurrency forensic process models include the use of digital forensics to examine and evaluate cryptocurrency transactions and activities. Identification, preservation, analysis, documentation, and evidence presentation are common phases in these frameworks. To investigate items, transaction history, source of financing, account and activity balances, and attribution, specialist blockchain forensic tools and standard forensic approaches are used. Asset tracing, which checks the whole history of a bitcoin account, is also a target of investigators. It is critical to adopt repeatable, documented processes to assure the integrity and admissibility of evidence in judicial proceedings.

The following are the steps of a digital forensics investigation that are also applicable to bitcoin forensic process models:

- Identifying the resources and technology used in the inquiry
- The generation of a forensic picture preserves the relevant data.

- Examination of the duplicated data
- The findings must be documented.
- The presentation of evidence

These phases are critical for assuring the data's integrity and acceptability in the court of law. Also, digital forensics is essential in detecting and demonstrating many sorts of wrongdoing, such as online crime, theft of information, safety breaches, hacking, and financial deception.

Table 8- Process of handling evidence

Phase	Description	Activities
Preparation	Prepare the foundation for the inquiry.	Define the investigation's scope and goals - Gather the appropriate staff, knowledge and equipment - To detect possible issues, do a risk assessment.
Incident Response	Protect and store evidence	Secure the incident site, including any digital evidence. - Keep a record of all observations, activities, and choices made during the investigation. - Establish and maintain a chain of custody for all evidence.
Data collection	Gather relevant data from various sources	Identify appropriate information sources, such as blockchain ledgers, wallets, and exchanges - Collect data from identified sources using suitable forensic techniques - Check the obtained data's integrity and validity.
Data processing	Preparation of data for analysis	Data should be cleaned, normalized, and transformed to improve its quality and consistency. - To enhance efficiency, remove duplicate or unnecessary data. - Arrange and organize data to facilitate analysis
Data analysis	Discover trends and findings in the data provided.	Data should be cleaned, normalized, and transformed to improve its quality and consistency. - To enhance efficiency, remove duplicate or unnecessary data. - Arrange and organize data to facilitate analysis
Reporting	Document and show results.	Summarize the key findings of the investigation - Provide detailed technical explanations of the analysis methods and outcomes - Incorporate charts,

		graphs, and other visual aids to enhance understanding
Presentation	Alert relevant stakeholders regarding the findings.	Clearly convey the results to investigators, legal teams, and appropriate authorities; provide expert evidence in court or other legal procedures; and maintain thorough record of the inquiry and conclusions.

D. Cryptocurrency forensics ISO Standards

There are currently no ISO standards for cryptocurrency forensics. There are however, a variety of ISO standards that may be utilized to aid Cryptocurrency forensics investigations. ISO standards provide a framework for performing digital forensics in a wide sense, embracing numerous sorts of digital evidence, including bitcoin transaction data. As the subject of cryptocurrency forensics evolves, new standards may be established to handle the unique problems and intricacies of analyzing blockchain and digital assets.

The following ISO standards are applicable to cryptocurrency forensic investigations:

- **ISO/IEC 27037:2012:** This standard establishes standards for particular actions in the management of digital evidence, such as the identification, collection, acquisition, and preservation of potentially relevant digital evidence. It provides people with assistance on frequent circumstances faced throughout the digital evidence handling process, as well as aids organizations in their disciplinary procedures and the transmission of possible digital evidence between jurisdictions.
- **ISO 21043-2:2018:** This standard outline forensic process standards for recognizing, documenting, collecting, transporting, and storing materials of possible forensic value. Although it is not directly relevant to data recovery operations from digital storage media (which are covered by ISO/IEC 27037), the storage medium itself can provide extra forensically valuable objects.
- **ISO/IEC 27037:** It is an international norm that specifies procedures for identifying, collecting, acquiring, and preserving digital evidence. This standard is part of the ISO/IEC 27000 series on information security management systems. ISO/IEC 27037 discusses the processes involved in processing digital evidence during an investigation, including cybersecurity events and digital forensics.
- **ISO/IEC 27041:2015:** It is a standard that gives guidelines on ensuring the acceptability and sufficiency of incident investigation procedures. It focuses on the mechanisms for ensuring that the procedures and processes employed in the investigation of information security events are "fit for purpose." This standard's major focus is on assurance for the forensic techniques and

instruments used in the examination of digital evidence. Credibility, trustworthiness, and integrity are important needs for any forensic methodologies, and this standard advances the assurance elements of evaluating digital evidence.

E. Data management and Ethics in Cryptocurrency forensics

In cryptocurrency forensics, data management and ethics entail treating digital evidence in a way that protects its integrity and admissibility in legal processes while complying to privacy and security regulations. In this process data management and ethics entail safely managing digital evidence, according to legal and privacy standards, preserving openness and documentation, adhering to professional codes of conduct, and engaging in continuous education and training. These considerations assure the quality and admissibility of evidence in judicial procedures while also protecting people' privacy and security rights. Some important elements of data management and ethics in cryptocurrency forensics are as follows:

- **Handling Digital Evidence:** Digital evidence such as transaction data, wallet information, and blockchain records are collected, analyzed, and interpreted during cryptocurrency forensic investigations. This evidence must be treated securely and with care to ensure its integrity and admissibility in judicial processes.
- **Compliance with Legal and Privacy Frameworks:** Cryptocurrency forensic investigations must adhere to legal and privacy frameworks, such as data protection laws and digital currency rules. This involves getting necessary warrants, respecting people's private rights, and complying to globally recognized legal norms.
- **Transparency and documentation:** Cryptocurrency forensic investigators should keep detailed documents of their investigative process, including the methodologies employed, evidence gathered, and conclusions reached. This material is critical for showing the investigation's legitimacy and dependability.
- **Ethical Considerations:** Cryptocurrency forensic investigators must follow professional rules of conduct and ethics, such as avoiding conflicts of interest, exposing any conflicts, and assuring the objectivity and impartiality of their work.
- **Continuing Education and Training:** Professionals interested in cryptocurrency forensics should participate in continuing education and training to keep current on technological advances, legal requirements, and best practices

V. DISCUSSION

As we discussed above, we provided a brief description of cryptocurrency forensics and explained the challenges which are possible in the following scenario and the countermeasures which can be taken against it to protect the following loopholes if present. We also covered some of the

ISO standards also so we safeguard ourself and provide some solutions to solve them.

A. Topics for the future of cryptocurrency forensics

Cryptocurrency forensics, or the utilization of forensic methods to cryptocurrency transactions, has developed as an important topic in dealing with digital currency crimes. As cryptocurrency acceptance grows, so does the demand for sophisticated forensic tactics to investigate and prosecute illegal activity. The future of bitcoin forensics will likely include numerous crucial areas that scholars and practitioners will investigate in order to handle rising difficulties and breakthroughs in the field.

Here are some of the important issues that bitcoin forensics research students might investigate:

- **Methodology Standardization:** The creation of standardized methodology for conducting cryptocurrency investigations is an ongoing field of study. This entails the use of specific techniques and technologies, as well as adherence to legal and privacy constraints.
- **Considerations for Privacy and Security:** As cryptocurrencies become more extensively utilized, privacy and security concerns are becoming increasingly essential. Researchers are looking into techniques to preserve the privacy and security of cryptocurrency transactions while yet allowing for forensic investigations in the event that they are required.
- **Artificial Intelligence Integration:** The incorporation of artificial intelligence (AI) into bitcoin forensic investigations is a topic of ongoing research. AI may be used to swiftly and correctly evaluate massive volumes of data, assisting investigators in identifying patterns and connections that might otherwise be missed.
- **Emerging Cryptocurrencies:** As new cryptocurrencies arise, academics are investigating and analyzing them. Developing new tools and approaches for tracking transactions and spotting trends is part of this.
- **Training and Education:** As the area of cryptocurrency forensics evolves, it is critical to maintain continual training and education. Researchers are looking into ways to give training and instruction to bitcoin investigators and other professionals.

B. Unsolved issues and future trends in cryptocurrency forensics

As the subject of cryptocurrency forensics evolves, a number of unresolved concerns and potential trends emerge. Practitioners as well as researchers are actively investigating these topics in order to overcome issues and keep up with changes in the bitcoin market. Despite substantial advances in bitcoin forensics, some unsolved challenges continue to impede the efficiency of cryptocurrency-related investigations and prosecutions.

The following are unresolved concerns and potential developments in bitcoin forensic investigations:

- **The evidentiary Value of Obtained results in Court:** The evidentiary value of obtained results in

court is still mostly unknown. The admissibility of forensic bitcoin investigation results in court processes must be clarified and established further.

- **Standardized Methodologies:** While a lot of steps has been taken to provide investigators with a defined approach for conducting cryptocurrency investigations, these methods require additional development and refinement to assure consistency and dependability in forensic operations.
- **Considerations for Privacy and Security:** As the use of cryptocurrencies evolves, there is a need to investigate new approaches for protecting the privacy and security of cryptocurrency transactions while yet allowing for effective forensic investigations when necessary.
- **Integration of Artificial Intelligence:** As an growing trend is the incorporation of artificial intelligence (AI) into bitcoin forensic investigations. More study is needed to investigate AI's potential for evaluating vast amounts of bitcoin data and detecting patterns and relationships.
- **Continuing Education and Training:** For professionals active in cryptocurrency forensics, ongoing training and education are vital. The provision of educational tools and research into successful training techniques can assist guarantee that investigators have the information and abilities needed to face the developing environment of cryptocurrency-related crime.

VI. CONCLUSION

Cryptocurrency forensics is a new profession that includes using digital forensics to examine and evaluate cryptocurrency transactions and activities. The usage of cryptocurrencies has increased dramatically in recent years, as has the demand for forensic investigations into cryptocurrency-related crimes. This research study investigated the present status of bitcoin forensics, with an emphasis on digital forensics investigations that aid law enforcement. The approaches addressed in this study highlight the complex dance between technology and research. The core of understanding the complexity of bitcoin transactions is blockchain analysis, address grouping, and heuristic techniques. In the face of privacy-centric cryptocurrencies, where the shadows of anonymity loom large, forensic professionals must innovate and adapt their methodologies to penetrate through strengthened privacy features. Future advancements in machine learning applications offer a more automated and efficient approach to pattern detection, taking into account the growing quantities and complexities of blockchain transactions. As cryptocurrencies become more extensively utilized, privacy and security concerns are becoming increasingly significant. Researchers are looking into techniques to preserve the privacy and security of cryptocurrency transactions while yet allowing for forensic investigations in the event that they are required. The evidentiary significance of collected findings in court is still mostly unknown, and additional clarification and establishment of the admissibility of forensic bitcoin research results in legal processes is required.

To summarize, cryptocurrency forensics is an important discipline that helps to discover and prove numerous sorts of wrongdoing, such as cybercrime, data theft, security breaches, hacking, and financial fraud. Standardized methodology, the use of artificial intelligence, and continual training and instruction are required to ensure the efficacy and trustworthiness of bitcoin forensic investigations in the future. Addressing privacy and security concerns, as well as explaining the evidence significance of collected conclusions in court, are also critical for cryptocurrency forensics' continuing success. As the use of cryptocurrencies evolves, so will the area of cryptocurrency forensics, and staying up to speed with the newest developments and trends will be critical to ensuring the integrity and admissibility of evidence in court.

VII. REFERENCES

- [1] S. Taylor, S. H.-y. Kim, K. A. Zainol Ariffin and S. N. H. Sheikh Abdullah, "A comprehensive forensic preservation methodology for crypto wallets," *Forensic Science International: Digital Investigation*, Vols. 42-43, p. 301477, October 2022.
- [2] S. Taylor, S. H.-y. Kim, K. A. Zainol Ariffin and S. N. H. Sheikh Abdullah, "A comprehensive forensic preservation methodology for crypto wallets," *Forensic Science International: Digital Investigation*, Vols. 42-43, p. 301477, October 2022.
- [3] D. P. Srivasthav, L. P. Maddali and R. Vigneswaran, "Study of Blockchain Forensics and Analytics tools," in *2021 3rd Conference on Blockchain Research & Applications for Innovative Networks and Services (BRAINS)*, Paris, 2021.
- [4] N. S. Semenov and S. R. Semenov, "Building information relations in the sphere of mining, cryptocurrency and crypto assets on the example of the Kyrgyz Republic," *Law Enforcement Review*, vol. 7, p. 75–84, June 2023.
- [5] R. Rajab Asaad, "Technical Analysis of Digital Currencies and the Most Important Indicators for Trading," *Academic Journal of Nawroz University*, vol. 11, p. 337–344, December 2022.
- [6] D. Phat, "ON THE QUESTION THE QUESTION ABOUT THE CIRCUMSTANCES SUBJECT TO PROVING WITHIN CRIMINAL FRAUD INVESTIGATIONS CIRCUMSTANCES SUBJECT TO PROVING WITHIN CRIMINAL FRAUD INVESTIGATIONS," in *Development of legal systems of Russia and foreign countries : problems of theory and practice*, Moscow, 2022.
- [7] A.-h. Park, H. Ryu, W. Park and D. Jeong, "Forensic investigation framework for cryptocurrency wallet in the end device," *Computers & Security*, vol. 133, p. 103392, October 2023.
- [8] A.-h. Park, H. Ryu, W. Park and D. Jeong, "Forensic investigation framework for cryptocurrency wallet in the end device," *Computers & Security*, vol. 133, p. 103392, 2023.
- [9] M. Z. Mas'ud, A. Hassan, W. M. Shah, S. F. Abdul-Latip, R. Ahmad, A. Ariffin and Z. Yunus, "A Review of Digital Forensics Framework for Blockchain in Cryptocurrency Technology," in *2021 3rd International Cyber Resilience Conference (CRC)*, Langkawi, 2021.
- [10] C. M. Joshi, *Cryptocurrency Forensics: 6 Important Aspects of investigation*, 2021.
- [11] M. Fröwis, T. Gottschalk, B. Haslhofer, C. Rückert and P. Pesch, "Safeguarding the evidential value of forensic cryptocurrency investigations," *Forensic Science International: Digital Investigation*, vol. 33, p. 200902, June 2020.
- [12] M. Fröwis, T. Gottschalk, B. Haslhofer, C. Rückert and P. Pesch, "Safeguarding the evidential value of forensic cryptocurrency investigations," *Forensic Science International: Digital Investigation*, vol. 33, p. 200902, June 2020.
- [13] M. Fröwis, T. Gottschalk, B. Haslhofer, C. Rückert and P. Pesch, "Safeguarding the evidential value of forensic cryptocurrency investigations," *Forensic Science International: Digital Investigation*, vol. 33, p. 200902, June 2020.
- [14] M. Fröwis, T. Gottschalk, B. Haslhofer, C. Rückert and P. Pesch, "Safeguarding the evidential value of forensic cryptocurrency investigations," *Forensic Science International: Digital Investigation*, vol. 33, p. 200902, June 2020.
- [15] S. Dudani, I. Baggili, D. Raymond and R. Marchany, "The current state of cryptocurrency forensics," *Forensic Science International: Digital Investigation*, vol. 46, June 2023.
- [16] S. Dudani, I. Baggili, D. Raymond and R. Marchany, "The current state of cryptocurrency forensics," *Forensic Science International: Digital Investigation*, vol. 46, p. 301576, September 2023.
- [17] S. Dudani, I. Baggili, D. Raymond and R. Marchany, "The current state of cryptocurrency forensics," *Forensic Science International: Digital Investigation*, vol. 46, p. 301576, September 2023.
- [18] S. Dudani, I. Baggili, D. Raymond and R. Marchany, "The current state of cryptocurrency forensics," *Forensic Science International: Digital Investigation*, vol. 46, p. 301576, September 2023.
- [19] S. Dudani, I. Baggili, D. Raymond and R. Marchany, "The current state of cryptocurrency forensics," *Forensic Science International: Digital Investigation*, vol. 46, p. 301576, September 2023.
- [20] K. De Welde, "Getting Physical: Subverting Gender through Self-Defense," *Journal of Contemporary Ethnography*, vol. 32, p. 247–278, June 2003.
- [21] F. Casino, N. Lykousas, V. Katos and C. Patsakis, "Unearthing malicious campaigns and actors from the blockchain DNS ecosystem," *Computer Communications*, vol. 179, p. 217–230, November 2021.
- [22] F. Casino, T. K. Dasaklis and C. Patsakis, "A systematic literature review of blockchain-based applications: Current status, classification and open issues," *Telematics and Informatics*, vol. 36, p. 55–81, March 2019.
- [23] A. Case and G. G. Richard, "Memory forensics: The path forward," *Digital Investigation*, vol. 20, p. 23–33, March 2017.
- [24] 14:00-17:00, *ISO/IEC 27037:2012*.